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Crack localization in beams by frequency shifts due to roving mass with rotary inertia

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Abstract

The problem of crack localization has been tackled in the past by detecting frequency changes due to the application of a mass appended to the structure. However the effect of the rotary inertia of the mass on the natural frequencies of a cracked beam has not been deeply investigated. In this paper a novel explicit closed form solution of the governing equation of a beam with a concentrated mass, with rotary inertia, in the presence of multiple cracks is proposed. Furthermore, an analytical proof to show that the natural frequencies of a cracked beam with a roving body with a rotary inertia will generally change abruptly as the body passes over a crack, provided that the crack permits differential flexural rotations, is presented. Numerical results in terms of natural frequencies are provided and the procedure to exploit the occurrence of frequency shifts to detect and locate each crack is described.

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1. Introduction

The problem of damage identification has been efficaciously addressed in the past by using vibrational measurements as described in the comprehensive review by Doebling et al. [1]. Mainly natural frequencies are monitored and precisely changes of frequency are usually understood as damage indicators. Unfortunately measurable frequency changes from the healthy to the damaged structure occur only in presence of significant damage and they are strongly affected by environmental noise and experimental uncertainties. With regard to beam-like structures,

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mode shape measurements have been proposed as additional data for crack identification in view of their capability to locate discontinuities at the cracked cross sections [2,3]. Moreover, mode shape changes induced by the cracks have been enhanced by the use of an appended roving mass in conjunction with the wavelet coefficients when applied to the differences between the undamaged and the damaged beams [4-7]. However, the adoption of mode shape measurements implies both analytical and experimental complications.

Another major issue related to the identification of concentrated cracks on beams is the a priori knowledge of the total number required by the available procedures. Hence a methodology able to deliver the exact number of concentrated cracks, as usually required by real applications, is desirable and presented in this work.

Precisely, the basic idea of this paper is considering a roving mass (at different positions at each test and not allowed to move axially during the frequency measurement) by considering the effect of its rotational inertia on frequency changes on a cracked beam. In fact, since a concentrated crack produces a rotation discontinuity at the cracked cross section, the rotational inertia of the concentrated mass induces a shift of the natural frequencies as the mass passes from one side to another of the crack. In order to prove the latter statement the exact solution of a beam with multiple cracks in presence of a concentrated mass (the translational and rotational inertia terms are both included) is presented. The latter solution is obtained by modelling each crack as an internal elastic rotational spring and making use of the distribution theory to deal with the presence of discontinuities [...].

A crack detection procedure, relying on the above mentioned frequency shifts, without any a priori knowledge of the number of cracks, is hence proposed. The procedure does not require any test execution (or even evaluation of the dynamic properties) on the healthy beam.

A first numerical investigation to show the performance of the proposed procedure based on the occurrence of frequency shifts to detect and locate each crack is finally presented.

2. A multi-cracked beam with a roving mass

The use of generalised functions, already adopted by some of the authors for cracked beams with no additional masses [12-16], has been proved to be an efficient approach to deal with along axis singularities in beams. In this section the generalized function approach is extended to account for the presence of a roving mass with translational and rotary inertia on beams with multiple cracks. The solution, proposed in explicit closed form, is unique and is provided in terms of four (boundary conditions dependent) integration constants only, that does not require any additional node, or continuity condition, at the cracked sections and at the mass location.

The proposed explicit closed form solutions allows to prove that frequency shifts occur at cracked cross sections induced by a concentrated roving mass with rotary inertia.

Let us consider an Euler-Bernoulli beam, referred to a spatial abscissa x spanning from 0 to the length L , with flexural stiffness EI and distributed mass m , in presence of multiple cracks at $x_i, i=1, \dots, n$, and an additional concentrated mass M_o with an eccentricity e at x_o . The presence of a concentrated mass M_o along a beam axis, placed at an eccentricity e , besides inducing a translational inertial force, activates also a rotational contribution accounting for the rotary inertia effect thus providing an inertia of $M_o e^2$.

The free vibration mode $\phi(\xi)$ of the beam is governed by the following fourth order differential equation:

$$\phi^{IV}(\xi) - \alpha^4 \phi(\xi) = \alpha^4 m_o \phi(\xi_o) \delta(\xi - \xi_o) - \alpha^4 m_o \varepsilon^2 \delta'(\xi - \xi_o) \phi'(\xi_o) + \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi''(\xi_i) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) \quad (1)$$

where $\delta(\bullet)$ is the well known Dirac's delta distribution and the apex indicates spatial differentiation with respect to the normalised abscissa $\xi = x/L$. Furthermore, in Eq. (4), $\alpha^4 = \omega^2 m L^4 / EI$ is the frequency parameter with ω circular frequency, while $m_o = M_o / (mL)$ represents the concentrated mass normalised with respect to the beam mass density and the beam length, finally $\varepsilon = e/L$ is the eccentricity of the mass normalised with respect to the beam length.

Eq.(1) has been specially devised to account for the influence of rotary inertia and translational inertia of the mass M_o by means of the terms $-\alpha^4 m_o \varepsilon^2 \delta'(\xi - \xi_o) \phi'(\xi_o)$ and $\alpha^4 m_o \phi(\xi_o) \delta(\xi - \xi_o)$, respectively. Furthermore, the summation term on the right side of Eq. (1) is due to the influence of the unknown rotational discontinuities

$\Delta\phi'(\xi_i) = \lambda_i\phi''(\xi_i)$ at the cracked cross sections with $\lambda_i = EI / (K_iL)$ being the normalised crack compliance that accounts for the spring rotational stiffness K_i equivalent to the i -th crack.

Eq.(1) can be straightforwardly and efficaciously integrated by employing the Laplace transform procedure to deal with the terms containing generalised functions. The solution is provided in an explicit form as follows:

$$\phi(\xi) = C_1f_1(\xi, \alpha) + C_2f_2(\xi, \alpha) + C_3f_3(\xi, \alpha) + C_4f_4(\xi, \alpha) \tag{2}$$

where

$$f_j(\xi, \alpha) = h_j(\xi, \alpha) + \bar{h}_o(\xi, \alpha)\alpha^4m_0f_j(\xi_o, \alpha) + \bar{h}_R(\xi, \alpha)\alpha^4m_0\varepsilon^2f_j'(\xi_o, \alpha) + \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{h}_k(\xi, \alpha)\lambda_k f_j''(\xi_k, \alpha) \tag{3}$$

$j = 1, \dots, 4$

$$h_1(\xi, \alpha) = \sin \alpha\xi; \quad h_2(\xi, \alpha) = \cos \alpha\xi; \quad h_3(\xi, \alpha) = \sinh \alpha\xi; \quad h_4(\xi, \alpha) = \cosh \alpha\xi;$$

$$\bar{h}_o(\xi, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2\alpha^3}[-\sin \alpha(\xi - \xi_o) + \sinh \alpha(\xi - \xi_o)]U(\xi - \xi_o)$$

$$\bar{h}_R(\xi, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2\alpha^2}[\cos \alpha(\xi - \xi_o) - \cosh \alpha(\xi - \xi_o)]U(\xi - \xi_o) \tag{4}$$

$$\bar{h}_k(\xi, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2\alpha}[\sin \alpha(\xi - \xi_k) + \sinh \alpha(\xi - \xi_k)]U(\xi - \xi_k)$$

In particular, the functions $h_k(\xi, \alpha), k = 1, \dots, 4$, represent the solution of the homogeneous beam, while $\bar{h}_o(\xi, \alpha), \bar{h}_R(\xi, \alpha), \bar{h}_k(\xi, \alpha), i = 1, \dots, n$, represent additional functions able to account for the presence respectively of the translational mass, the rotary inertia, and the cracks.

The integration constants appearing in the solution in Eq.(1) can be obtained by imposing the relevant boundary conditions. In particular, for the case of a clamped-clamped beam, fully analyzed in the following applications, the following determinantal equation is derived:

$$[f_3(1, \alpha) - f_1(1, \alpha)][f_4'(1) - f_2'(1, \alpha)] - [f_4(1, \alpha) - f_2(1, \alpha)][f_3'(1, \alpha) - f_1'(1, \alpha)] = 0 \tag{5}$$

Eq.(5) can be solved numerically in terms of the frequency parameter α . The roots of the equation provide the fundamental frequencies of the beam, and allow to compute the integration constants and to derive the corresponding mode shapes.

Based on Eq.(5), it can be proved that the determinantal equation of a cracked beam undergoes an abrupt change when a concentrated mass with rotary inertia crosses a crack, that implies the occurrence of a frequency jump.

In fact, for the case of a clamped-clamped beam with a single crack ($n = 1$) at ξ_1 , the $f_j(1, \alpha)$ functions and their first derivatives appearing in Eq.(5) can be written as:

$$f_j(1, \alpha) = h_j(1, \alpha) + \bar{h}_o(1, \alpha)\alpha^4m_0f_j(\xi_o, \alpha) + \bar{h}_R(1, \alpha)\alpha^4m_0\varepsilon^2f_j'(\xi_o, \alpha) + \bar{h}_1(1, \alpha)\lambda_1 f_j''(\xi_1, \alpha)$$

$$f_j'(1, \alpha) = h_j'(1, \alpha) + \bar{h}_o'(1, \alpha)\alpha^4m_0f_j(\xi_o, \alpha) + \bar{h}_R'(1, \alpha)\alpha^4m_0\varepsilon^2f_j'(\xi_o, \alpha) + \bar{h}_1'(1, \alpha)\lambda_1 f_j''(\xi_1, \alpha) \tag{6}$$

$j = 1, \dots, 4$

where $f_j(\xi_o, \alpha), f_j'(\xi_o, \alpha), f_j''(\xi_o, \alpha)$ depend on whether the mass is located before or beyond the crack. In particular the latter terms take the following form:

$$f_j(\xi_o, \alpha) = h_j(\xi_o, \alpha) \quad , \quad f'_j(\xi_o, \alpha) = h'_j(\xi_o, \alpha) \quad , \quad f''_j(\xi_1, \alpha) = h''_j(\xi_1, \alpha) + \bar{h}''_R(\xi_1, \alpha) \alpha^4 m_o \varepsilon^2 f'_j(\xi_o, \alpha) \quad (7)$$

$$j = 1, \dots, 4$$

when the mass is located on the left of the crack (i.e. $\xi_o = \xi_1^-$), while they take the following form

$$f_j(\xi_o, \alpha) = h_j(\xi_o, \alpha) \quad , \quad f'_j(\xi_o, \alpha) = h'_j(\xi_o, \alpha) + \bar{h}'_1(\xi_o, \alpha) \lambda_1 f''_j(\xi_1, \alpha) \quad , \quad f''_j(\xi_1, \alpha) = h''_j(\xi_1, \alpha) \quad (8)$$

$$j = 1, \dots, 4$$

when the mass is on the right of the crack (i.e. $\xi_o = \xi_1^+$).

Comparing Eqs.(7) and (8), accounting for the definitions in Eqs.(3),(4) reveals that the functions $f'_j(\xi_o, \alpha), f''_j(\xi_1, \alpha)$ change in view of additional terms, depending on whether the mass is on the left or the right side of the crack. Hence, the discontinuous form of the determinantal equation (5), when the mass crosses a crack position, is strictly due to the presence of the rotary inertia and leads to the occurrence of frequency shifts.

Without loss of generality, the boundary conditions relative to clamped-clamped beams are those employed in this paper; however the achieved conclusions do not depend on the considered boundary conditions.

3. Numerical evidence for crack localization

As proved in section 2 the presence of a roving mass with rotary inertia is able to provide an abrupt jump of the natural frequencies as the mass crosses each crack. In principle, the measurement of the first fundamental frequency is generally sufficient to effectively detect the crack positions. However it will be shown in this section that, accounting for higher frequencies, enhances the presence of cracks. In particular, in this section a numerical investigation of a beam with multiple cracks in the presence of a roving mass is conducted based on the explicit solution formulated in Eq.(2). The presented numerical investigation leads to the proposal of crack detection procedure relying on the existence of jumps affecting the natural frequencies, to be measured by free vibration tests, as the concentrated mass changes its position along the beam span.

In the first sub-section, the case of a clamped-clamped single cracked beam is analyzed to provide numerical evidence of the frequency shift caused by the rotary inertia as the mass crosses the crack. In the second sub-section the case of a beam with multiple cracks is considered in order to show that the considered procedure is not limited to single cracked beams and the main feature of the proposed detection procedure is maintained even with several cracks.

3.1. Single crack

The case of a clamped-clamped beam with a single crack located at $\xi_1 = 0.7$ is presented here. The crack severity is $\lambda_1 = 1$, while the normalized concentrated mass and eccentricity are $m_o = 0.05$ and $\varepsilon = 0.1$, respectively. In Fig.1 the first three fundamental frequencies (in terms of the frequency parameter α^2) are presented as a function of the roving mass position ξ_o . Three different cases are considered: 1. beam without concentrated mass (red line); 2. beam with concentrated mass with rotary inertia effect neglected (green line); 3. beam with concentrated mass accounting for the rotary inertia effect (black line).

Fig. 1. Single-cracked beam: frequency parameter α^2 vs mass position for the first three frequencies.

It may be noted that the crack has caused a reduction in the natural frequencies for all modes, irrespective of the mass location and, as expected, for each considered configuration the frequency curve, when the rotary inertia effect is neglected, is bounded from above and below by the cases with no additional mass and that with rotary inertia included, respectively.

In particular, the presence of the translational mass with rotary inertia neglected causes a first derivative discontinuity in the frequency curve as the mass position coincides with the crack location. However, the latter property is hardly recognizable and is not definitely suggested for crack location purposes unless wavelet transform is applied to the measured signal to enhance any sort of irregularity [6, 17-21].

On the contrary, as shown in Fig.1, as main novelty of the present study, for all considered modes, there is a sudden jump in the frequency vs mass location plot as the mass possessing rotary inertia passes the crack.

In Fig.2 the dependency of the frequency jump from various parameters to assess their influence on the dynamic behaviour of a single cracked beam is studied. In particular, By considering the i -th frequency parameter at the left $(\alpha_i^-)^2$ and right $(\alpha_i^+)^2$ sides of the crack (located at ξ_1), and the corresponding frequency parameter $(\alpha_i^o)^2$ in absence of any additional concentrated mass, the following normalised frequency jump $\Delta\alpha_i^2$ is plotted in Fig.2:

$$\Delta\alpha_i^2 = \frac{(\alpha_i^+)^2 - (\alpha_i^-)^2}{(\alpha_i^o)^2} \tag{10}$$

The parametric study reported in Fig.2 is concerning with the clamped-clamped case reported in Fig.1 (i.e. $\xi_1 = 0.7$, $\lambda_1 = 1$, $m_o = 0.05$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$).

Fig. 2. Single cracked clamped-clamped beam ($\lambda_1 = 1$), relative frequency jumps for the first five frequencies vs: (a) crack position, (b) crack compliance, (c) mass entity and (d) eccentricity sensitivities.

In Fig.2a the normalized frequency jump is shown as a function of the crack location ξ_1 . Generally speaking the maximum value of the frequency shift increases as higher frequencies are considered. Furthermore, the normalized

frequency jump crosses the zero axis for all the frequencies, for symmetric reasons, when the crack is located at $\xi_1 = 0.5$.

In Fig.2b the crack compliance has been considered variable in the range $0 \leq \lambda_1 \leq 1$. It is worth noting that, as the crack compliance increases, the frequency jump increases in magnitude except in a restricted region involving small cracks for the case of the fifth frequency.

In Fig.2c the dependence of the normalised frequency jump with respect to the mass ($0 \leq m_o \leq 1$) is considered. Even in this case the trend in the frequency jumps as the mass increases is not always regular, as the third and fourth frequency demonstrate.

Finally, in Fig.2d the effect of the eccentricity ($0 \leq \varepsilon \leq 1$) is assessed. Again, the trend of the frequency jump is not always monotonic.

3.2. Multiple cracks

Finally, in order show how the proposed procedure is effective even in presence of a large number of cracks, a clamped-clamped beam with $n = 10$ equally spaced cracks is investigated. All the cracks have the same severity ($\lambda_i = 0.1$), while the mass and eccentricity are $m_o = 0.05$ and $\varepsilon = 0.1$, respectively.

In Fig.3 the first five fundamental frequencies (in terms of the frequency parameter α^2) are shown as a function of the mass position ξ_o for the cracked beam. The same three different cases as in the previous applications are considered.

The results in Fig.3 show how, even in presence of a considerable number of cracks, the abrupt jump due to the rotary inertia effect can be easily noticed at each passage of the mass over each crack.

Fig. 3. Multi-cracked beam: frequency parameter α^2 vs mass position for the first five frequencies.

3.3. File naming and delivery

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4. Conclusions

A novel procedure for identifying the crack locations in beams, that makes use of the effect of the rotary inertia of a roving body on the natural frequencies of a beam as it passes a crack, has been presented. Precisely, a proof based on the Dynamic Stiffness Matrix and numerical results for specific beams show that: a roving body possessing rotary inertia introduces a discontinuity in the frequency vs roving body location relationship at crack locations if the crack allows a relative rotation between adjacent sections, except at positions that lie on a line of structural symmetry. Furthermore, due to the inertial action arising from the product of the inertia and the square of the frequency, the magnitude of discontinuity in the frequency vs roving body location plots increases with mode number.

Numerical evidence of the above proof have been provided for beams with single and multiple cracks by presenting a novel closed form solution for multiple cracked beams with an additional mass that allows a straightforward parametric analysis requiring the evaluation of the boundary conditions only.

The presented results in terms of the frequency shift and a cumulative frequency parameter jump have been discussed to lay the theoretical basis for the future development of a proper damage detection technique.

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